

1 **A synthesis of bias and uncertainty in sap flow methods**

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15 **Abstract**

16 Sap flow measurements with thermometric methods are widely used to measure
17 transpiration in plants. Different method families exist depending on how they apply heat
18 and track sapwood temperature (heat pulse, heat dissipation, heat field deformation or heat
19 balance). These methods have been calibrated for many species, but a global assessment of
20 their uncertainty and reliability has not yet been conducted. Here we perform a meta-
21 analysis of 290 individual calibration experiments assembled from the literature to assess
22 calibration performance and how this varies across methods, experimental conditions and
23 wood properties (density and porosity types). We used different metrics to characterize
24 mean accuracy (closeness of the measurements to the true, reference value), proportional
25 bias (resulting from an effect of measured flow on the magnitude of the error), linearity in
26 the relationship between measurements and reference values, and precision (reproducibility
27 and repeatability). We found a large intra- and inter-method variability in calibration
28 performance, with a low proportion of this variability explained by species. Calibration
29 performance was best when using stem segments. We did not find evidence of strong
30 effects of wood density or porosity type in calibration performance. Dissipation methods
31 showed lower accuracy and higher proportional bias than the other methods but they
32 showed relatively high linearity and precision. Pulse methods also showed significant
33 proportional bias, driven by their overestimation of low flows. These results suggest that
34 Dissipation methods may be more appropriate to assess relative sap flow (e.g., treatment
35 effects within a study) and Pulse methods may be more suitable to quantify absolute flows.
36 Nevertheless, all sap flow methods showed high precision, allowing potential correction of
37 the measurements when a study-specific calibration is performed. Our understanding of

38 how sap flow methods perform across species would be greatly improved if experimental
39 conditions and wood properties, including changes in wood moisture, were better reported.

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41 Keywords: Sap flow, methods, calibrations, meta-analysis, error, bias

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43 **1. Introduction**

44 Quantifying transpiration of vegetation is of major importance for hydrological, ecological,
45 and agricultural sciences, since it represents 60-80% of the water that returns from the land
46 surface to the atmosphere (Jasechko et al., 2013; Schlesinger and Jasechko, 2014; Wei et
47 al., 2017). The study of transpiration and its environmental sensitivity is essential to
48 understand vegetation water cycling (Frank et al., 2015; Konings et al., 2017; Novick et al.,
49 2016) and to forecast changes in vegetation functioning and composition under climate
50 change (Allen et al., 2015). Addressing these questions requires non-destructive
51 measurements of whole-plant transpiration at multiple timescales (Wullschleger et al.,
52 1998). Thermal methods of sap flow measurement show a number of advantages over other
53 methods such as those based on isotopes tracing or leaf gas exchange (Smith and Allen,
54 1996), and have become the most widely used approach to estimate tree-level transpiration
55 (Poyatos et al. 2016) (Fig. S1). When compared against independent estimates of
56 evapotranspiration components, sap flow methods have provided reasonable qualitative and
57 quantitative results (Diawara et al. 1991, Hogg et al. 1997, Kool et al. 2014, Schlesinger
58 and Jasechko 2014, Zhang et al. 2014, but see Wilson et al. 2001, Oishi et al. 2008,
59 Shimizu et al. 2015). However, sap flow measurements may be subject to various potential

60 sources of error. Some of these errors are related to scaling sap flow variability both within
61 trees and from tree to stand level (Hatton et al., 1995; Hernandez-Santana et al., 2015;
62 Mitchell et al., 2009), while others are related to intrinsic limitations of the methods or to
63 how these methods are applied (see Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2013). Although these
64 biases have been studied, they have not yet been quantified globally and there is no
65 conclusive assessment of how they differ across methods or species characteristics,
66 including wood properties (Poyatos et al., 2016).

67 Sap flow methods (Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2013) can measure sap flow rate (SF, g h^{-1}
68 or equivalent units) or sap flux density (i.e., sap flow rate per unit sapwood area, SFD, cm^3
69 $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ or equivalent units) in a plant's conductive tissue and can be classified in four
70 families depending on how they heat the sapwood and how they measure sapwood
71 temperatures: (1) the Dissipation family, including thermal dissipation (TD; Granier, 1985)
72 and transient thermal dissipation (Do and Rocheteau, 2002a, TTD; 2002b) methods, which
73 measure the dissipation of heat from a heated probe inserted in the sapwood with reference
74 to a reference, non-heated probe; (2) the Pulse family, including the compensation heat
75 pulse (CHP; Swanson and Whitfield, 1981), heat ratio (HR; Burgess et al., 2001), T-max
76 (Cohen et al., 1981), calibrated average gradient (CAG; Testi and Villalobos, 2009),
77 sapflow+ (SF+; Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2012a, 2012b), single probe heat pulse (SPHP;
78 López-Bernal et al., 2017) and dual heat pulse methods (Dual; Pearsall et al., 2014), which
79 all apply heat in pulses and track sapwood temperature changes caused by thermal
80 convection and conduction; (3) the Field family, including the heat field deformation
81 (HFD; Nadezhdina, 2018; Nadezhdina et al., 1998) and its derivatives, which measure the
82 shape changes of a continuous heat field in the sapwood, using axial and tangential probes;

83 and (4) the Balance family, represented by stem heat balance (SHB; Daum, 1967;
84 Sakuratani, 1981; Vieweg and Ziegler, 1960) and trunk heat balance (THB; Čermák et al.,
85 2004, 1973) methods, which measure the energy balance across a heated wood section.
86 This latter family is the only one directly measuring sap flow rate, while all the others
87 measure sap flux density.

88 Methodological errors in sap flux density measurements may be caused by wounding
89 following probe insertion into the sapwood (except for the miniaturized non-invasive ones;
90 see (Clearwater et al., 2009; Hanssens et al., 2013; Schreel and Steppe, 2018), biological
91 variation in wood parameters and diverse raw data processing approaches (Oishi et al.,
92 2016; Peters et al., 2018; Vergeynst et al., 2014). Wounding affects heat and water
93 transport and thus may disrupt sap flow measurements (Barrett et al., 1995; Burgess et al.,
94 2001; Green et al., 2009, 2003; Green and Clothier, 1988; Steppe et al., 2015), especially
95 during long-term installations (Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2018; Wiedemann et al., 2013).
96 While wound corrections have been available for a long time for some Pulse family
97 methods (Green et al., 2003; Swanson and Whitfield, 1981), they have only become
98 recently available for other methods such as TD (Wiedemann et al., 2016). Sap flux density
99 methods are also affected by changes in radial patterns, which are not constant over time,
100 so these methods have to measure the entire sapwood depth by sufficiently large probes, or
101 by individual measurement points at different depths (Hatton, 1990). Although some
102 methods have a more solid theoretical background based on the physics of thermal
103 transport (Pulse and Balance methods), all of them rely on a certain degree of empiricism,
104 which may introduce errors caused by biological variability and/or variation in signal
105 processing approaches: species-specific empirical calibrations in Dissipation methods

106 (Fuchs et al., 2017), zero-flow determination or baselining (Lu et al., 2004; Peters et al.,
107 2018), and different parameterization of thermal sapwood properties in Pulse and Field
108 methods (Chen et al., 2012). These thermal sapwood parameters could change over time,
109 introducing further errors in the measurements (e.g. changes in stem water content;
110 Vergeynst et al., 2014). Within the Balance family, those using external heating do not
111 suffer from potential errors due to wounding, but they all require zero-flow determination
112 (Smith and Allen, 1996). Balance methods have often been considered to better integrate
113 spatial variability in sap flow (Čermák et al., 2004), but whether they perform generally
114 better than sap flux density methods remains unknown.

115 Other errors in sap flow measurement may result from not accounting properly for method-
116 specific assumptions. For many sap flow methods, natural temperature gradients (NTG)
117 need to be minimized and/or accounted for to obtain unbiased estimates of sap flow (Reyes-
118 Acosta et al., 2012; Vandegehuchte et al., 2015). Incorrect sensor geometry (misalignment)
119 affects the accuracy of the measurements (Burgess et al., 2001; Cabibel et al., 1991; Ren et
120 al., 2017; Swanson, 1983; Swanson and Whitfield, 1981). Other application errors, such as
121 those arising from the incomplete contact of TD probes with the sapwood (Clearwater et
122 al., 1999) are difficult to prevent, though they can be reasonably corrected a posteriori (e.g.
123 Clearwater correction, Hultine et al., 2010; Paudel et al., 2013). Despite that these
124 application errors have been well described in individual studies, a general quantification of
125 these errors for the most employed sap flow methods is currently lacking.

126 Comparisons of sap flow measurements with respect to a reference method (hereafter, for
127 simplicity, ‘sap flow calibrations’) are usually aimed at obtaining species-specific
128 calibrations (Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2013) to assess different parameterizations of

129 wood thermal properties (Vandegehuchte et al., 2012) or to validate empirical corrections
130 (e.g., wounding, NTG, changes in water content, misalignment; Burgess et al., 2001;
131 Vergeynst et al., 2014). Although few studies calibrate multiple sap flow methods for
132 different species (Fuchs et al., 2017), collectively these calibration studies have shown the
133 inherent limitations of different sap flow methods to deal with low (Green et al., 2003) or
134 high flows (Green et al., 2009). Variability and quality in calibration performance may also
135 be related to specific wood properties such as wood density (Suleiman et al., 1999;
136 Wullschleger et al., 2011), especially given the fact that wood density enters the calculation
137 of sap flux density for some methods (Vandegehuchte et al., 2012) and co-varies with wood
138 moisture content (Looker et al., 2016). Because thermal properties of wood are dependent
139 on both, i.e. wood density and moisture content (MacLean, 1941), they might additionally
140 be influenced by wood anatomical traits such as wood porosity type, i.e. coniferous,
141 diffuse-porous or ring-porous wood. In conifers, however, no clear effects of wood density
142 on calibration variability have been reported (Peters et al., 2018). Therefore, a quantitative
143 synthesis of sap flow calibrations, accounting for variation caused by different flow ranges
144 and wood properties is needed to generalize and understand the patterns observed in
145 individual calibration studies.

146 Here, we compile a global database of published sap flow calibrations to quantify the
147 measurement errors associated with different sap flow methods and to assess the factors
148 underlying variability across methods. In assessing calibrations, we distinguished between
149 mean systematic bias (*accuracy*), a measure of the average degree of closeness of the
150 measurements to the value obtained with a reference method; *proportional bias*, which
151 occurs when the magnitude of the error is a function of the flow; *linearity* in the

152 relationship between measurements and values obtained with a reference method; and
153 *precision*, a measure of reproducibility and repeatability. Our main objective is to assess the
154 differences in *accuracy*, *proportional bias*, *linearity* and *precision* among methodological
155 families and individual sap flow methods; in addition, we will determine whether
156 calibration performance across methods is associated with species wood traits (wood
157 density and porosity type).

158

159 **2. Methods**

160 *2.1 Sap flow calibration datasets*

161 We retrieved sap flow calibration studies of the seven most common methods (CHP, T-
162 max, HR, HFD, SHB, TD, TTD) applied on trees, palms or lianas, using standard database
163 searching tools (i.e. Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar). The search was
164 conducted in June 2017 applying the following keywords: *sap fl**, *sap flux density*,
165 *calibration*, *potomet**, *gravimet**, *thermal dissipation*, *heat pulse*, *heat balance*, *heat field*
166 *deformation*, *compensation heat pulse*, *T-max*, and their combinations. Other sources of
167 data were obtained from the references of previously collected studies. For each calibration
168 experiment, we obtained paired observations of sap flow, measured with a thermal method
169 and with an independent reference method (typically gravimetric or volumetric). Data was
170 digitized from published figures (using GetData Graph Digitalizer version 2.26.0.20). We
171 asked the authors to supply the raw data when these were unavailable from the original
172 publication. We obtained data from 60 studies (see Table S1) reporting 374 individual
173 calibration experiments performed on 81 different shrub and trees species (10,186 data
174 points in total). In the analysis, we only used calibrations that were properly applied

175 according to our definition below (i.e. 290 calibrations out of 374) to restrict the variability
176 to the intrinsic characteristics of the methods.

177 We always considered sap flow observations obtained with the original parameters of the
178 methods (e.g. Granier's original calibration for TD), without applying the coefficients
179 derived from the calibrations themselves. Some calibrations with TD gave measured K
180 values (i.e. sap flow index, calculated from raw sapwood temperature differences) instead
181 of measured SFD and, in these cases, K values were transformed to SFD using Granier's
182 original equation and calibration coefficients (Eq. 1, $a = 42.84 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, $b = 1.231$)
183 (Granier, 1985).

$$184 \quad SFD = a \times K^b \quad (1)$$

185 For each calibration, we recorded the type of calibration material: whole plants, whole
186 plants without roots or cut stem segments. We also assessed whether the sap flow method
187 was properly applied using the best available protocol specified for each method. We
188 considered a proper application of Dissipation methods when the probe was shorter than the
189 sapwood depth and radial profile correction was applied, when the probe was
190 approximately equal to the sapwood depth, or when the probe was longer than the sapwood
191 depth and this effect was corrected for following Clearwater *et al.* (1999). To test whether
192 our results could have been affected by this correction, we performed a preliminary analysis
193 with the same structure as the main statistical model (cf. section 2.3) comparing TD
194 calibrations with or without the Clearwater correction and we did not find significant
195 effects on any of the metrics of calibration performance (cf. section 2.2) (data not shown).
196 We considered a proper application of Pulse methods when wound correction was applied
197 and either the probe had multiple measuring points along the sapwood or a radial sap flow

198 profile correction was applied. We always considered Balance methods and Field methods
199 as properly applied, because they always integrate (or account for) spatial variability of sap
200 flow.

201 Finally, to analyze the influence of wood traits on calibration performance we used wood
202 density, defined as fresh volume over oven-dry mass, and wood porosity type of the species
203 employed in each study. Wood density was supplied in only a few studies (7 species ~ 80
204 calibration experiments ~ 4 studies). Assuming that for wood density between-species
205 variability is typically larger than within-species variability (Siefert et al., 2015; Vilà-
206 Cabrera et al., 2015), we retrieved wood density of each species from the TRY database
207 (Kattge et al., 2011). Wood densities of *Carica papaya*, *Phoenix dactylifera* and *Vitis*
208 *vinifera* were obtained from Kempe (2014), Fathi (2014) and Castelan-Estrada (2002),
209 respectively, as they were not recorded in TRY. When wood density could not be found for
210 a given species, we used the phylogenetically nearest species of the same genus if available
211 in TRY (10 of 81 species; e.g. *Citrus sinensis* for *Citrus reticulata*). We could not estimate
212 wood density for three taxa (*Humulus lupulus*, *Musa sp.* and *Siagrus romanzoffiana*). A
213 correlation between calibration-specific and species-level wood density extracted from the
214 TRY database ($r = 0.78$, $P < 0.01$, $n = 12$ calibrations, 6 species) indicates that species-level
215 wood density values indeed are applicable for our purpose, but the results should be
216 interpreted with caution. Finally, wood porosity was obtained from the InsideWood
217 database (InsideWood 2004, Wheeler, 2011), using four categories: ring-porous, diffuse-
218 porous (i.e. diffuse and semi-diffuse porous), conifer and monocots.

219 *2.2 Calibration assessment*

220 Although the reference methods always provide an estimate of sap flow through plants or
221 stem segments, sap flow measurements can be reported as SF or SFD. It was not possible
222 for us to interconvert between SF and SFD in all cases because sapwood areas were not
223 always reported. This precluded a joint analysis of all the paired observations in the same
224 linear model because units differ between SF and SFD. To overcome this problem and to
225 maximize the amount of data considered in the analyses, we first evaluated calibration
226 performance using four complementary dimensionless metrics at the calibration level,
227 which allowed us to analyze globally all calibrations regardless of the magnitude they
228 reported (SF or SFD). In a second stage, we quantified the variability in the absolute errors
229 in sap flow measurements across methods and flow ranges separately for SF and SFD
230 methods. We did not expect differences between calibrations reported with SF or SFD
231 because the inter-conversion between them only involves a scalar transformation. In
232 addition, preliminary analyses confirmed that there was no significant difference between
233 SF and SFD for any of the calibration performance metrics reported in this study (Table
234 S2).

235 For the global analysis, the following metrics were calculated for each calibration (SF and
236 SFD): the average ln ratio (*Ln-Ratio*) between measured and reference values as a measure
237 of overall accuracy; the slope of the relationship between measured and reference sap flow
238 to characterize proportional bias (*Slope*); the slope of the ln-ln relationship between
239 measured and reference sap flow as a measure of linearity (*Slope (ln-ln)*); and Z Pearson's
240 Correlation to describe precision (*Z-Cor*) (Fig. 1). To calculate these metrics, we filtered
241 out data points with measured or reference flows less or equal to 0. All calibration metrics
242 and subsequent statistical models were performed in R 3.4.2 (R Core Team, 2017). For

243 model-based metrics, we always checked residuals to ensure they satisfied normality and
 244 homoscedasticity assumptions.

245 *Accuracy* was evaluated as the mean of the natural logarithm of the ratio between paired
 246 measurements (j) of each calibration (i):

$$247 \quad Ln - Ratio_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \ln\left(\frac{measured_j}{reference_j}\right)}{n_i} \quad (2)$$

248 where $measured_j$ and $reference_j$ are the paired measurements of sensor-estimated and
 249 reference flow, respectively, and n the number of paired measurements for each calibration
 250 i (see Fig. 1). The *Ln-Ratio* varies between $-\infty$ and $+\infty$, and equals 0 for a calibration with
 251 perfect mean accuracy (i.e. lack of systematic bias). We also expressed this metric as the
 252 exponential of *Ln-ratio* minus one multiplied by 100, as an indicator of accuracy deviation
 253 (in %).

254 The slope of the linear relationship (Eq. 3) describes how the magnitude of the error
 255 changes (linearly) as a function of the reference flow. The slope of the ln-ln relationship
 256 (Eq. 4) captures the linearity between the measured and the reference flow. Both slope
 257 estimates were calculated for each calibration using a simple linear regression (lm -
 258 package stats):

$$259 \quad measured_{ij} \sim \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1i} reference_{ij} + e_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$260 \quad \ln(measured_{ij}) \sim \beta'_{0i} + \beta'_{1i} \ln(reference_{ij}) + e_{ij} \quad (4)$$

261 where β_{0i} and β'_{0i} are the intercepts and β_{1i} and β'_{1i} are the slopes for each calibration (i),
 262 and j indicates individual calibration points. Hereafter, we will refer to β_{1i} as *Slope* and to
 263 β'_{1i} as *Slope (ln-ln)*; slope values equal to 1 characterize measurements without
 264 proportional bias (Eq. 3) and with high linearity (Eq. 4), respectively.

265 We used Pearson's correlation coefficients r between measured and reference flow of each
 266 calibration experiment (i) as a metric to describe the precision of the methods. The
 267 distribution of the resulting variable was skewed due to the large amount of correlation
 268 coefficients close to 1, so we used Fisher's Z transformation (Eq. 5) to achieve normality:

$$269 \quad Z - Cor_i = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+r_i}{1-r_i} \right) \quad (5)$$

270 Low values of *Z-Cor* correspond to low r correlations, and high values of *Z-Cor* correspond
 271 to high r correlations and thus high precision (data set range $r = [0.0491 - 0.9999]$; $r =$
 272 $0.0491 \sim z = 0.0491$; $r = 0.9999 \sim z = 5.1594$).

273 In the analysis of the absolute errors of sap flow measurements, we calculated the
 274 Normalized Root Mean Square Error (*NRMSE*) for each calibration (i) (Eq. 6), separately
 275 for SFD and SF methods, in order to obtain the percentage of absolute error at the mean
 276 range of each calibration (i).

$$277 \quad NRMSE_i = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (measured_j - reference_j)^2}{n}} \right)_i \times 100 / range\ mean_i$$

278 (6)

279 Subsequently, from the NRMSE and the mean range of each calibration, we fitted a linear
280 model for each method allowing to quantify the absolute error (RMSE) at a given sap flow
281 and also to obtain a RMSE at a reference flow (cf. section 2.3).

282 *2.3 Statistical analyses*

283 All the analyses were performed using linear mixed-effects models (LMM) with the
284 package lmer (Bates et al., 2015). Least-square means were estimated with package
285 lsmeans (Lenth, 2016) and used to summarise the effects of fixed factors and to test
286 contrasts among predictions. In all models, we used the variables *Study* and *Species* as
287 partially crossed random effects (Schielzeth and Nakagawa, 2013), as we are interested in
288 taking into account the variability associated with study and species, and also to analyze
289 within- and between-group variability. We used *Study* as we expect experimental variability
290 between researchers or laboratories, and *Species* because calibration performance has been
291 reported to vary across species (Fuchs et al., 2017; Smith and Allen, 1996; Steppe et al.,
292 2015). For each model, R^2_m and R^2_c (marginal and conditional coefficients of determination,
293 respectively) based on Nakagawa & Schielzeth (2013) were calculated using the function
294 r.squaredGLMM of the package MuMIn (Barton, 2017) in R. Intraclass Correlation
295 Coefficients (ICC) were also calculated for the random factors to quantify the proportion of
296 variance within and among groups (low ICC implies high intra-group variability).

297 In a first analysis, we were interested in assessing the differences in calibration metrics (*Ln-*
298 *Ratio*, *Slope*, *Slope (ln-ln)*, *Z-Cor*) between different families of methods (*Family*: Pulse,
299 Dissipation, Balance and Field methods), because methods within a family share similar
300 physical principles. We also analyzed differences between individual methods with a
301 sufficient sample size (*Method*: CHP, T-max, HR, HFD, SHB, TD, TTD). As the

302 calibration material determines, to a large extent, the experimental conditions, we also
303 included this variable in our models (*Material*: whole plants, whole plants without roots or
304 cut stem segments). For the analysis of absolute errors of sap flow measurements, we
305 modelled NRMSE as a function of *Method* and the *Mean Range* of SFD (or SF for Balance
306 methods) in each calibration, as well as their interaction. We used the same random
307 structure as in previous models.

308 Finally, we assessed how each calibration metric depended on *Wood Density* and *Wood*
309 *Porosity*. A first model included all methods available, with *Method* interacting with *Wood*
310 *Density* as predictors. In order to test *Wood Porosity* effects, we fitted separate models for
311 CHP and TD calibrations, as these two methods were the only ones that had enough data (>
312 5 calibrations) for more than one type of porosity. Separate models were needed because
313 not all wood porosity types were represented for all methods. In both models we also
314 included *Material* as an explanatory cofactor, and the same random structure as in the first
315 analysis explained above.

316

317 **3. Results**

318 Most of the published calibrations were performed with Pulse and Dissipation methods
319 (Table 1). In particular, 61% of the total number of the properly applied calibrations were
320 conducted using TD or CHP, followed by HFD and HR. SHB, T-max and TTD methods
321 were less represented, with 8 – 14 calibrations each. The metrics extracted from the raw
322 calibrations were highly variable within methods (Fig. 2). Calibration metrics often
323 followed a quasi-normal distribution, but in most cases distributions were truncated or
324 skewed, particularly for methods with fewer calibrations (Fig. 2).

325 *3.1 Calibration performance compared among methods and families of*
326 *methods*

327 The average accuracy deviation across sap flow methods (properly applied) ranged between
328 14.2% for CHP and -40.5% for TD (Table 1). There were significant differences in
329 accuracy (*Ln-Ratio*) among families of methods and for methods but not for calibration
330 materials (Fig. 3). The Dissipation family in general and the TD and TTD methods in
331 particular were the only cases for which the *Ln-Ratio* was significantly different from 0
332 ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3), indicating systematic bias (underestimation).

333 Proportional bias, estimated by *Slope*, varied among methods and families of methods
334 ($p < 0.01$). Among families, Dissipation methods showed a significantly smaller *Slope* than
335 Pulse and Field methods (Fig. 3(a)), which was largely driven by the low value of TD (Fig.
336 3(b)). Also, both Pulse and Dissipation families had slopes significantly different from 1
337 ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively), but only the slope of the TD method was significantly
338 lower than 1 ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3). As for the effects of calibration material, calibrations made
339 with whole plants had a significant proportional bias (*Slope* < 1, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3).

340 Calibration linearity, as denoted by *Slope (ln-ln)*, varied across methods and families of
341 methods ($p < 0.001$). We observed higher values of *Slope (ln-ln)* for the TD method
342 compared to CHP, T-max, HR and HFD. Consistently, the Dissipation family in general
343 also had a higher *Slope (ln-ln)* than the Pulse and Field families (Fig. 3). CHP, T-max and
344 HFD (and Pulse and Field methods in general) had a *Slope (ln-ln)* significantly lower than 1
345 (Table 1 and Fig. 3(b)), indicating a convex relationship between reference and measured

346 flow. Calibrations performed with whole plants suffered from lack of linearity, indicated by
347 *Slope (ln-ln)* significantly lower than 1 (Fig. 3).

348 Precision (*Z-Cor*) was explained by both method and calibration material. The HFD
349 method (and Field methods in general) provided significantly higher precision than either
350 Pulse or Dissipation methods (particularly CHP, TD and TTD) (Table 1 and Fig. 3(b)).
351 Calibrations performed on stem segments provided higher precision than those conducted
352 on whole plants (with or without roots) (Fig. 3).

353 In all the previous models, little variability was explained by species ($\tau_{00, \text{species}}$), relative to
354 the higher variability associated to *Study*, particularly for the *Ln-Ratio* and *Z-Cor* models
355 ($\tau_{00, \text{study}}$, Table S3). This is consistent with the low ICC values observed for the species
356 factor, indicating that there is more variability within than among species (Table S3).

357 In addition, the analysis of the normalized absolute error for the different methods showed
358 that *NRMSE* decreased linearly with increasing measured sap flow in CHP, HFD and TTD
359 methods and increased for T-max, SHB and TD (Table 2 and Fig. S2). For HR the increase
360 in *NRMSE* with measured sap flow was not significant. For all the methods that measure
361 SFD, the absolute error at a typical flow of $25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ ranged between $6.3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$
362 for CHP and $10.7 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ for the TTD method (Table 2).

363 *3.2 Influence of wood traits*

364 We did not find any significant influence of wood density on accuracy and linearity metrics
365 (Fig. 4). Nonetheless, we observed a negative effect of wood density on proportional bias
366 of HFD and TD calibrations ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.1$, respectively). In addition, a significant

367 positive effect of wood density on the precision of HFD measurements was observed
368 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the higher the wood density, the higher the precision (Fig. 4).

369 We did not find any significant difference among wood porosity types in calibration
370 metrics for studies using the TD or CHP methods. Nevertheless, the non-linearity (*Slope*
371 ($\ln\text{-}\ln$) < 1) observed in general for the CHP method (Fig. 3(b)) was only significant for
372 species with diffuse-porous wood, not for conifer species (Table 3).

373

374 **4. Discussion**

375 Our results show a large variability in the quality of sap flow calibrations, even within the
376 same sap flow method (Fig. 2), highlighting the large variability among and even within
377 studies. This implies that, even if methods are properly applied (as defined in section 2.1),
378 sap flow measurements can still produce biased estimates of water transport rates in plants,
379 and these errors will need to be considered in quantitative analyses based on this type of
380 measurements. On average, however, all sap flow methods assessed here produced results
381 that may be acceptable for qualitative use in most applications, as shown by the typical high
382 correlation between measured and reference values ($r > 0.89$ for all methods and method
383 families, Table 1). For quantitative use, no method appears to be suitable for all
384 experimental contexts, and researchers need to consider both the inherent limitations of the
385 methods and the need to perform study-specific calibrations (see Implications and
386 recommendations, Table 4).

387 *4.1 Sap flow measurement errors across methods and methodological families*

388 A relatively small part of the total variability in the quality of calibrations is related to
389 methods and families of methods and, to a lesser extent, to the calibration material (fixed
390 effects explain 8 – 28% of the variability in calibration metrics; see R^2_m values in Table
391 S3). Despite the high variability within methods, we detected significant differences
392 between methods. Dissipation methods were the only methods for which accuracy was
393 significantly lower than expected for an ideal calibration. This is consistent with previous
394 reports (Braun and Schmid, 1999; Bush et al., 2010; Caterina et al., 2014; Chan, 2015; de
395 Oliveira Reis et al., 2006; Fuchs et al., 2017; Lu and Chacko, 1998; McCulloh et al., 2007;
396 Montague and Kjelgren, 2006; Rubilar et al., 2017; Steppe et al., 2010; Taneda and Sperry,
397 2008; Uddling et al., 2009) and our synthesis confirms that most of the individual TD and
398 all TTD calibrations underestimate sap flow systematically (Fig. 5). Interestingly, however,
399 other studies have found the opposite result (Cain, 2009; Hultine et al., 2010; Lu, 2002;
400 Sperling et al., 2012; Sun et al., 2012) and simulation models (Hölttä et al., 2015;
401 Wullschleger et al., 2011) suggest that it is difficult to state a priori whether TD will over-
402 or underestimate flow, as the measurements obtained are highly dependent on wood
403 properties and on flux conditions. Our results show that, globally, the conditions leading to
404 underestimation are more frequent and support the existence of a proportional bias
405 underlying this systematic underestimation by TD (Fig. 3). It must be also noted, however,
406 that Dissipation methods have been tested against a much wider range of flow conditions
407 compared to the rest of the methods (Fig. 5, Fig.6).

408 Calibration parameters of the TD method were originally considered to be universal but
409 subsequent studies have claimed that species-specific calibrations are necessary to obtain
410 correct sap flow measurements (Fuchs et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2004; Steppe et al., 2010). For

411 a set of diffuse-porous species, using a pooled calibration also substantially improved TD
412 (but not HFD) performance compared to measurements obtained with the original
413 calibration (Fuchs et al., 2017). However, our results show that species in general and wood
414 porosity type in particular explain a small or even no proportion of the variability in the
415 calibrations (Table 3 and S3). This implies that factors related to the experimental context
416 and, possibly, to intraspecific variability in wood properties (cf. section 4.2) may have a
417 large contribution to overall uncertainty. Therefore, our results suggest that calibration
418 parameters for TD or HFD, obtained under different experimental contexts, may not be
419 generalizable to species level, as also suggested by Fuchs et al. (2017).

420 In addition to Dissipation methods, Pulse methods also suffer proportional bias, probably
421 driven by overestimation at low flows, although this was significant for T-max only (i.e.
422 positive intercepts in linear models fitted to calibration data; Fig. 5 and 6 and S3). It is well
423 known that the equations of CHP and T-max cannot be solved at sap flows close to 0, and
424 the calibration intercepts observed here (Fig. S3) are consistent with the detection
425 thresholds reported for T-max ($\sim 10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$; Green et al., 2003) and CHP ($2\text{-}4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2}$
426 h^{-1} ; Bleby et al., 2004; Green et al., 2003). Our results confirm and generalize a previously
427 reported low-flow detectability problem for T-max (Green et al., 2009, 2003;
428 Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2012a), but we could not confirm it for CHP as described
429 before (Barrett et al., 1995; Becker, 1998; Bleby et al., 2004; Vandegehuchte and Steppe,
430 2012a). Despite overestimation at low flows, the average accuracy of CHP and T-max is
431 good, which implies that low-flow overestimations may be compensated with
432 underestimations at high flows. This is also shown by the lack of linearity observed in both
433 methods (*Slope (ln-ln) < 1*; Fig. 3(b)).

434 Our analysis did not detect the saturation effect for the HR method at high flows that has
435 been reported elsewhere (Bleby et al., 2008; Green et al., 2009; Steppe et al., 2015). This is
436 likely due to the fact that HR calibrations considered here include few observations in the
437 region where this overestimation occurs ($> \sim 45 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$; Figs 5 and 6). Moreover, the
438 high variability in the calibrations probably precluded detection of the saturation effect
439 (Fig. 3 and 5) and of the apparent trend of increasing *NRMSE* with sap flow range for HR
440 (Table 3 and Fig. S2). A lack of linearity can also be observed for HFD, consistent with the
441 suggested tendency of this method to underestimate at high flows (Vandegehuchte and
442 Steppe, 2012c).

443 Despite the large variability in precision within methods, our results show that calibrations
444 performed with HFD give more precise results than those conducted using the CHP, TD
445 and TTD methods. Although this result should be interpreted with care as it is based on 57
446 calibrations but only from 3 studies, the higher precision observed with HFD could lie in
447 the second dimension included in the method, which could better capture the effect of
448 anisotropy of the wood structure. This would also be consistent with the fact that SHB, a
449 method that is assumed to integrate sap flow variability within the stem, was the method
450 with the second highest precision on average, albeit precision was very variable for this
451 method (Fig. 3(b)).

452 We did not detect differences in accuracy, proportional bias or linearity of the calibrations
453 across calibration materials. However, compared to an ideal calibration, we did find
454 proportional bias and lack of linearity in calibrations performed on whole plants, probably
455 because these calibrations use large scales whose sensitivity and resolution are usually low,
456 potentially affecting low-flow measurements and leading to artefactual overestimation at

457 low flows. Poor linearity may also be due to non-linear changes in belowground hydraulic
458 resistance as the sap flow increases (Martínez-Vilalta et al., 2007). In cut plants, we may
459 have two opposite effects, as cutting could eliminate belowground resistance (favoring
460 flow) but add resistance due to putative embolism formation after cutting. Similarly, the
461 higher precision of calibrations conducted on cut stems relative to those conducted on
462 whole plants (with and without roots), likely reflects that cut stem calibrations are normally
463 conducted in laboratories with precision scales and under controlled conditions that
464 minimize experimental random errors.

465 *4.2 The performance of sap flow calibrations is largely unrelated to species*
466 *wood traits*

467 Species-specific wood density and wood porosity type explained little variability in overall
468 calibration performance, although we detected some effects of wood density for HFD and
469 TD calibrations. Wood density affected HFD measurements by increasing precision, which
470 could be related to the response time of the sensors. If we assume that maximum sapwood
471 water content is reduced as wood density increases (Simpson, 1993), associated changes in
472 thermal diffusivity could lead to a faster sensor response (Hölttä et al., 2015), higher
473 correlation between actual and measured flows. Wood density also showed a negative
474 relationship with proportional bias for HFD and TD, a pattern that could be caused by the
475 combined effects of wood density and water content on wood thermal diffusivity
476 (Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2012c; Vergeynst et al., 2014). The fact that we did not find
477 clear effects of wood density on calibration accuracy and linearity, despite that wood
478 density affects thermal diffusivity and hence heat transport (Wullschleger et al., 2011),
479 could be explained by two reasons. Firstly, we could not use the actual wood density for

480 most of the calibrations, because it was not reported in the corresponding studies, and using
481 species-level averages instead of the wood density of the plant material specifically used on
482 the calibrations may mask the effect of wood density on calibration performance. Secondly,
483 wood density in angiosperms appears to be only weakly correlated to some wood properties
484 that could be important for sap flow calibrations, such as lumen fraction (Zanne et al.,
485 2010).

486 Our global analysis did not show clear and consistent differences in calibration quality
487 between different wood porosity types (Table 2) as previously suggested by several studies
488 for both CHP (Green and Clothier, 1988) and TD methods (Bush et al., 2010; Sun et al.,
489 2012). According to heat transport theory, we should expect declining performance from
490 conifer to ring-porous species (i.e. from most homogenous to most heterogeneous wood).
491 For CHP, we found that proportional bias (only marginally) and nonlinearity departed from
492 an ideal calibration for diffuse-porous species, but these patterns did not differ significantly
493 from those observed for conifers. Our results did not clearly support either an inferior
494 performance of TD in ring-porous species compared to diffuse-porous or conifers, as could
495 be expected from the reported underestimation driven by large sap flow gradients along
496 sensor length or by the imperfect probe contact with hydroactive xylem in species with
497 narrow sapwood (Clearwater et al., 1999; but see Wullschleger et al., 2011). Wood porosity
498 effects on sap flow calibrations have been inferred in individual studies from measurements
499 in few species representative of each wood porosity type (Bush et al., 2010; Sun et al.,
500 2012; Xie and Wan, 2018) and our inability to detect these effects here may be caused by
501 the high variability in experimental context within our dataset. Furthermore, the effect of
502 the different anatomies may be masked by high structural variability within wood porosity

503 types, as for example the variation in latewood to earlywood in conifers (Fan et al., 2018)
504 and we cannot discard that calibration performance could be related to quantitative
505 anatomical traits not assessed in this study (cf. Xie and Wan, 2018). Although the low
506 variability we observed at the species level suggests that quantitative anatomical traits
507 might not explain much of the variability in sap flow calibrations, we encourage that
508 quantitative wood traits are measured in the same plant material used to calibrate sap flow
509 sensors to better understand the influence of wood properties on the variability of sap flow
510 calibrations.

511 *4.3 Implications and recommendations*

512 Our global analysis shows that even when the methods are applied following standard
513 recommendations the quality of individual calibrations can be very low (Fig. 3). This result
514 reflects, on one hand, systematic bias in TD and lack of linearity in CHP, two of the most
515 widely used methods (Fig. S1) and, on the other hand, unknown sources of error related to
516 experimental conditions and/or sample characteristics (Table 4). In our study, we could not
517 account for all the experimental conditions to evaluate these sources of variability, except
518 for the effect of the calibration material. Examples of factors that may affect calibrations
519 when using the same type of calibration material include sensor design (Fuchs et al., 2017),
520 sensor installation (Bleby et al., 2004; Lu and Chacko, 1998; Ren et al., 2017), variation in
521 calculations of wood thermal properties (Looker et al., 2016), zero flow determination
522 (Looker et al., 2016; Peters et al., 2018) or the mechanism of flow generation in cut stem
523 calibrations (negative vs positive pressures) (Fuchs et al., 2017) (Table 4). Previous reports,
524 however, usually focus on only one of the sources of experimental error. Importantly,
525 relevant methodological information that could be used to assess (and account for) these

526 sources of error is frequently not reported (Peters et al., 2018; Steppe et al., 2015). Clearly,
527 further research into the effects of experimental conditions on the quality of different sap
528 flow methods should be a priority, as well as more complete, standardized reporting of
529 experimental conditions, including information on the sources of potential methodological
530 errors listed in Table 4.

531 Our results show that calibrations may be needed to obtain correct absolute values of sap
532 flow, even when Pulse methods are used (see also Fuchs et al., 2017; Steppe et al., 2010).
533 However, sap flow calibrations provide a snapshot of the performance of a given sap flow
534 method under relatively stable conditions, which may greatly differ from those experienced
535 by plants in the field. Moreover, our analysis could not address the methodological
536 variability related to more dynamic effects such as errors caused by changes in sapwood
537 water content (Vergeynst et al., 2014), long-term wounding or signal dampening (Marañón-
538 Jiménez et al., 2018; Peters et al., 2018; Wiedemann et al., 2013). In this sense, more
539 studies should assess calibration applicability to mid- or long-term measurements (e.g.,
540 Oliveras and Llorens, 2001), possibly combined with independent estimates of sapwood
541 water content (Vandegheuchte and Steppe, 2012a) and whether calibrations obtained from
542 excised segments are valid for whole-plants.

543 Considering only their performance in calibration tests (i.e. no other logistic or technical
544 issues, such as sensor, datalogging, or power constraints, which will be study-specific) we
545 can provide some general recommendations on the use of sap flow methods (Table 4). The
546 most widely used method, TD, appears to be consistently inaccurate, shows proportional
547 bias and generally underestimates sap flow, by 40% on average (if used with its original
548 calibration coefficients). However, it presents good linearity, which implies that this

549 method can be used when sap flow responses to environmental variables and/or treatments
550 are the primary focus of the study (i.e., good estimates of absolute sap flow values are not
551 critical). In comparison, CHP, T-max and HFD all present a certain nonlinearity which may
552 affect the estimation of these environmental responses. At least for CHP and T-max
553 (specially for the latter) this pattern seems to be driven by overestimation at low flows and
554 underestimation at high flows canceling out each other. This implies that both Pulse
555 methods could be suitable for studies interested in absolute values of transpiration. For the
556 HFD method, the nonlinearity could be influencing the estimations of radial sap flow
557 patterns, as these measurements would need to correctly measure both high and low flows
558 simultaneously. We also confirm that the HR method may not be suitable to measure high
559 flows but it is probably the best method for detailed physiological studies involving low
560 flows.

561 *4.4. Conclusions*

562 In conclusion, our global assessment contributes towards a proper incorporation of
563 measurement errors in the interpretation of individual case studies and in modelling studies
564 aimed at upscaling sap flow data (Hatton et al., 1995; Hernandez-Santana et al., 2015).
565 Perhaps even more importantly, it paves the way towards improved intercomparison of sap
566 flow datasets obtained with different methods to assess regional or global patterns in plant
567 water use (e.g., the SAPFLUXNET initiative; Poyatos et al., 2016). Although providing
568 explicit correction factors for each method is beyond the scope of this paper, the typical
569 accuracy deviations provided in Table 1 can be used as a first order correction when
570 combining sap flow data from different methods (and no additional information on study-
571 specific uncertainty sources is available).

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1026 Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the calibration performance metrics used in the analyses.

1027 Each panel presents the same simulated calibration points, representing plausible data. Blue

1028 dots represent an accurate, unbiased, linear and precise calibration, while red dots represent

1029 an inaccurate, biased, non-linear and imprecise calibration.

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1032 Fig. 2. Distribution of the calibration performance metrics for each method. Dots represents
 1033 the value of each individual calibration metric. Crosses represent the average of the metric
 1034 for each method. Horizontal, dashed lines specify reference, perfect calibration values for a
 1035 given metric.

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1039 Fig. 3. Predictions of the LMM models calculated from least-squares means of the four
 1040 calibration metrics (*Ln-Ratio* as a proxy for mean accuracy, *Slope* for proportional bias,
 1041 *Slope (ln-ln)* for linearity and *Z-Cor* for precision) for (a) different families of sap flow
 1042 methods or for (b) different sap flow methods and for different calibration materials
 1043 (Segment: stem segment; Whole plant: whole plant on a container or lysimeter; No-roots:
 1044 whole plant without roots). 95% confidence intervals of the estimates are also shown.
 1045 Different letters indicate significant differences between factors levels evaluated with
 1046 Tukey’s test. Horizontal, dotted lines indicate reference, perfect calibration values for a
 1047 given metric. Asterisks (*) indicate significant departure from those reference values.

1048

1049 Fig. 4. Relationship between the four calibration performance metrics (*Ln-Ratio* as a proxy
 1050 for accuracy, *Slope* for proportional bias, *Slope (ln-ln)* for linearity, and *Z-Cor* for
 1051 precision) and wood density, for different sap flow methods. Horizontal, dashed red lines
 1052 indicate reference, perfect calibration values for a given metric. Regression lines are shown
 1053 for significant effects only, and the corresponding level of significance (p-value: <0.1: (.),
 1054 <0.05: (*), < 0.01: (**), < 0.001: (***)) is also reported

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 1057 Fig. 5 Relationship between measured and reference sap-flux density (SFD) for different
 1058 sap flow methods, studies and calibrations. The fits of ln-ln regressions (Eq. 4) for each
 1059 calibration are also depicted. Different colors represent different studies that report results
 1060 in sap-flux density units. Scales vary across panels to facilitate intra method comparison.
 1061 The red dotted line indicates the 1:1 relationship.

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1066 Fig. 6. Relationship between measured and reference sap flow (SF) for different sap flow
 1067 methods, studies and calibrations. The fits of ln-ln regressions (Eq. 4) for each calibration
 1068 are also depicted. Different color symbols and line types represent different studies. Scales
 1069 varies across panels to facilitate intra method comparison. Insets are shown in some panels
 1070 (T-max, SHB, TD) to facilitate visualization when the flow ranges differed markedly
 1071 among calibrations for the same method. The red dotted line indicates 1:1 relationship.

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1078 Table 1. Analysis summary for the different methods and families of methods obtained
 1079 from the LMM models (least-squares means). We provide the four dimensionless metrics:
 1080 the *Ln-ratio* as a measure of accuracy, the accuracy deviation calculated as the exponential
 1081 of the *Ln-ratio* minus one multiplied by 100, the *Slope* to characterize the proportional bias,
 1082 the slope of the ln-ln-relationship, *Slope (ln-ln)*, as a measure of linearity, and Z Pearson's
 1083 correlation (*Z-Cor*) to describe overall precision; n: number of calibrations; studies: number
 1084 of studies of each method; species: number of different species; r is the correlation
 1085 calculated as the tanh of *Z-Cor*.

<i>Method</i>	<i>Family</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>studies</i>	<i>species</i>	<i>Ln-Ratio</i>	<i>Accuracy deviation %</i>	<i>Slope</i>	<i>Slope (ln-ln)</i>	<i>Z-Cor</i>	<i>r</i>
CHP	Pulse	63	16	21	0.133	14.225	0.887	0.783	1.837	0.950
T-max	Pulse	11	5	6	-0.053	-5.162	0.614	0.697	1.755	0.942
HR	Pulse	23	6	7	-0.145	-13.498	0.845	0.841	2.000	0.964
HFD	Field	57	3	4	-0.073	-7.040	0.901	0.782	2.378	0.983
SHB	Balance	8	5	6	-0.242	-21.494	0.847	0.967	2.287	0.980
TD	Dissipation	115	18	35	-0.519	-40.488	0.683	1.066	1.711	0.937
TTD	Dissipation	14	2	6	-0.493	-38.921	0.669	0.985	1.464	0.899
all	Pulse	97		30	0.012	1.167	0.844	0.787	1.874	0.954
all	Field	57		4	-0.008	-0.820	0.896	0.762	2.322	0.981
all	Balance	8		6	-0.244	-21.650	0.854	0.972	2.294	0.980
all	Dissipation	129		37	-0.464	-37.153	0.681	1.052	1.666	0.931

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1088 Table 2. Error analysis of different sap flow methods. The normalized root mean square
 1089 error (*NRMSE*) is modelled as a function of method and the mean flow range for each
 1090 calibration (and their interaction) using a LMM model with the same random structure as
 1091 the main models (cf. section 2.3). β_0 and β_1 are the corresponding intercepts and slopes,
 1092 respectively (β_0 expressed as % *NRMSE*; β_1 expressed as % *NRMSE* per change in cm^3
 1093 $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ for SFD or as % *NRMSE* per change in $\text{cm}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$ for SF). This linear model, was
 1094 also used to calculate a reference *NRMSE* at a sap flux equivalent to the percentile 50 of the
 1095 range of the data in the calibrations (SFD: $25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; SF: $1300 \text{ cm}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$). The expected
 1096 *NRMSE* and *RMSE* (in brackets, in $\text{cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, except for SHB that is in $\text{cm}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$) at a
 1097 typical flow are also given.

<i>Method</i>	<i>NRMSE</i>		
	β_0 %	β_1	<i>reference NRMSE</i> (<i>and RMSE</i>)
CHP	27.03***	-0.08***	25.04% (6.26)
T-max	31.56.	0.25***	37.83% (9.46)
HR	9.38	0.81	29.59% (7.40)
HFD	30.33***	-0.12***	27.45% (6.86)
SHB	14.85	0.02***	42.95% (558.36)
TD	34.93***	0.10***	37.31% (9.33)
TTD	44.04***	-0.04***	42.94% (10.73)

1098 Significant codes: 0.1: '.', 0.05: '*', 0.01: '**', 0.001: '***'

1099 Table 3. Least-squares means and 95% CI calculated from the LMM models testing the
 1100 effect of different wood porosity types (*Wood porosity*) on sap flow calibration
 1101 performance metrics (*Ln-Ratio* as a proxy for accuracy, *Slope* for proportional bias, *Slope*
 1102 (*ln-ln*) for linearity, and *Z-Cor* for precision) for CHP and TD methods. No differences
 1103 were detected among wood anatomies. Significance levels indicate departure from an ideal
 1104 calibration (*Ln-Ratio* = 0; *Slope* = 1; *Slope (ln-ln)* = 1)

<i>Method</i>	<i>Wood porosity</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Accuracy Ln-Ratio</i>	<i>Proportional bias Slope</i>	<i>Linearity Slope (ln-ln)</i>	<i>Precision Z-Cor</i>
CHP	diffuse	48	-0.055 [-0.370 , 0.259]	0.795 [0.557 , 1.033].	0.799 [0.671, 0.927] **	1.980 [1.729 , 2.231]
	conifers	15	0.066 [-0.603 , 0.734]	1.043 [0.459 , 1.627]	0.777 [0.469 , 1.085]	1.381 [0.775 , 1.988]
TD	diffuse	81	-0.273 [-0.658 , 0.111]	0.752 [0.491 , 1.014].	1.126 [0.917 , 1.336]	1.672 [1.085 , 2.260]
	ring	16	-0.405 [-0.866 , 0.056].	0.743 [0.410 , 1.077].	0.984 [0.681 , 1.286]	2.260 [1.572 , 2.947]
	conifers	15	-0.396 [-0.873 , 0.080].	0.808 [0.468 , 1.147]	1.142[0.842 , 1.441]	1.606 [0.892 , 2.321]

1105 Significant codes: 0.1: ‘.’, 0.05: ‘*’, 0.01: ‘**’, 0.001: ‘***’

1106 Table 4. Synthesis of the potential sources of error and use adequacy for each method.
 1107 Crosses indicates that the method is sensitive to the respective source of error (updated
 1108 from Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2013). Methods are classified according to their use
 1109 effectiveness under different flow conditions: dark grey, light grey and white indicate
 1110 highly, partially and no recommended use, respectively. When assessing use adequacy for
 1111 high/low flows, dark and light gray indicate a Normalized Root Mean Square Error
 1112 (NRMSE) less than a 22% and a 44%, respectively, calculated with the NRMSE model
 1113 (Table 2). In *Absolute flows* use recommendation, dark grey shows methods with both
 1114 accuracy (*Ln-Ratio*) and proportional bias (*Slope*) not significantly different from a perfect
 1115 calibration. In *Relative flows* use recommendation, dark grey shows methods with linearity
 1116 (*Slope (ln-ln)*) not significantly different from a perfect calibration and with reasonable
 1117 precision. Potentiality of measuring small stems diameters (< 125mm) is also reported.

Method	Potential source of measure error									Effectiveness in measuring					
	Wounding	Radial velocity profile	Wood properties	Natural thermal gradients	Sensor installation	Sensor design	Baselining	Power input	Pulse length	Reverse flows	Low flows*	High flows*	Absolute flows	Relative flows	Small stems
CHP	x	x	x	x	x				x						
T-max	x	x	x		x		x								
HR	x	x	x		x										
HFD	x	x		x	x	x	x	x							
SHB				x			x	x							
TD	x	x	x	x		x	x	x							
TTD	x	x	x	x		x	x	x							

1118 *(Low/High: SFD methods: <5 / >80 cm³ cm⁻² h⁻¹; SF methods: <260 / >3900 cm³ h⁻¹)

1119

1120 Fig. S1. Representation of the cumulative number of studies using different sap flow
 1121 methods between 1957 and 2017 (adapted and updated from Poyatos et al. 2016). CAG:
 1122 calibrated average gradient; CHP: compensation heat pulse (early heat pulse methods have
 1123 been considered CHP, Edwards et al. 1997); HFD: head field deformation; HR: heat ratio,
 1124 SF+: sapflow+; SHB: stem heat balance; TD: thermal dissipation; THB: trunk heat balance;
 1125 Tmax: T-max heat pulse; TTD: transient thermal dissipation. Notice the logarithmic scale
 1126 on the y-axis.

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1129 Fig. S2. Relationship between root mean square error (RMSE) and sap flux density (mean
 1130 calibration range) and for different sap flux density methods, as predicted by the LMM
 1131 model presented in Table 3.

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1134 Fig. S3. Predictions of the LMM models calculated from least-squares means of the
 1135 intercept (β_0) of the linear model (Eq. 3). Different letters indicate significant differences
 1136 between factors levels evaluated with Tukey's test. Horizontal, dotted lines indicate
 1137 reference, perfect calibration values for a given metric. Asterisks (*) indicate significant
 1138 ($p < 0.05$) departure from those reference values.

1139

1140 Table S1. Summary table of the studies used in the analyses presented in the paper. Sap
 1141 flow method, species, calibration material, porosity and average stem/tree diameter are
 1142 reported.

<i>Study</i>	<i>Method</i>	<i>Species</i>	<i>Calibration material</i>	<i>Wood porosity</i>	<i>Diameter (cm)</i>
Alarcon <i>et al.</i> 2005	CHP	<i>Citrus limon</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	2.5
Ballester <i>et al.</i> 2011	CHP	<i>Citrus clementina</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	NA
Barret <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Corymbia maculata</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	NA
Bleby <i>et al.</i> 2004	CHP	<i>Eucalyptus marginata</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	10.0
Bleby <i>et al.</i> 2004	HR	<i>Eucalyptus marginata</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	10.0
Braun and Schmid 1999	TD	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	whole plant	Ring-porous	3.8
Burgess <i>et al.</i> 2001	HR	<i>Eucalyptus marginata</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	NA
Bush <i>et al.</i> 2010	TD	<i>Populus fremontii</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	5.1
Bush <i>et al.</i> 2010	TD	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.8
Cain 2009	TD	<i>Macaranga hypoleuca</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	82.0
Cain 2009	TD	<i>Macaranga pearsonii</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	67.0
Caspari <i>et al.</i> 1993	CHP	<i>Pyrus serotina</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	6.6
Caterina <i>et al.</i> 2013	TD	<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	8.0
Chan 2015	TD	<i>Abies concolor</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	6.0
Cohen <i>et al.</i> 1981	T-max	<i>Platanus orientalis</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	6.7
Cohen <i>et al.</i> 1981	T-max	<i>Populus alba</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	6.7
Cohen <i>et al.</i> 1998	T-max	<i>Malus domestica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	NA
Dragoni <i>et al.</i> 2005	CHP	<i>Malus domestica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	6.5
Dye <i>et al.</i> 1996	CHP	<i>Pinus patula</i>	without roots	Coniferous	NA
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	7.8
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	10.4
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Olea europaea</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	8.2
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Olea europaea</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	9.8
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	8.0
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 2006	CHP	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	7.0
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 1999	CHP	<i>Olea europaea</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	8.8
Fernandez <i>et al.</i> 1999	CHP	<i>Olea europaea</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	NA
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HFD	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	10.6
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HFD	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.4
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HFD	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.3
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HR	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	10.4
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HR	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.3
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	HR	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.9
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Acer campestre</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	11.8

Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	10.8
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.8
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Populus nigra</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	10.8
Fuchs <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.4
Gonzalez-Altozano <i>et al.</i> 1998	CHP	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	11.5
Gonzalez-Altozano <i>et al.</i> 1998	T-max	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	11.5
Granier 1985	TD	<i>Pinus nigra</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	4.5
Granier 1985	TD	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	4.5
Granier 1985	TD	<i>Quercus pedunculata</i>	stem segment	Ring-porous	4.5
Green <i>et al.</i> 1988	CHP	<i>Actinidia chinensis</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	5.3
Green <i>et al.</i> 1988	CHP	<i>Actinidia chinensis</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	5.4
Green <i>et al.</i> 1988	CHP	<i>Malus sylvestris</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	5.6
Gutierrez-soto <i>et al.</i> 2012	HR	<i>Carica papaya</i>	whole plant	Monocot	NA
Gutierrez <i>et al.</i> 1994	SHB	<i>Acacia koa</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	NA
Gutierrez <i>et al.</i> 1994	SHB	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	NA
Hatton <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Eucalyptus populnea</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	5.4
Heilman <i>et al.</i> 1990	SHB	<i>Ligustrum japonicum</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	1.0
Herbs <i>et al.</i> 2007	TD	<i>Acer campestre</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Herbs <i>et al.</i> 2007	TD	<i>Crataegus monogina</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Hultine <i>et al.</i> 2010	TD	<i>Tamarix ramossissima</i>	stem segment	Ring-porous	4.2
Intrigliolo <i>et al.</i> 2009	T-max	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	whole plant	Ring-porous	NA
Isarangkool <i>et al.</i> 2009	TTD	<i>Citrus maxima</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	5.1
Isarangkool <i>et al.</i> 2009	TTD	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.7
Isarangkool <i>et al.</i> 2009	TTD	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.4
Johan Uddling <i>et al.</i> 2009	TD	<i>Betula papyrifera</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Lu 2002	TD	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	4.0
Lu 2002	TD	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	2.3
Lu 2002	TD	<i>Musa spp.</i>	whole plant	Monocot	12.0
Lu and Chacko 1998	TD	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	2.3
Madurapperuma <i>et al.</i> 2009	HR	<i>Syagrus romanzoffiana</i>	whole plant	Monocot	NA
Michell <i>et al.</i> 2009	HR	<i>Eucalyptus capillosa</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	6.5
Montague <i>et al.</i> 2006	TD	<i>Liquidambar styraciflua</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	5.3
Montague <i>et al.</i> 2006	TD	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	5.6
Montague <i>et al.</i> 2006	TD	<i>Pyrus calleryana</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	6.6
Montague <i>et al.</i> 2006	TD	<i>Quercus robur x Q. bicolor</i>	whole plant	Ring-porous	5.7
Nadezhdina <i>et al.</i> 1998	HFD	<i>Tilia cordata</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	12.0
Nortes <i>et al.</i> 2009	CHP	<i>Prunus dulcis</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	15.0
Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TD	<i>Malus domestica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.0
Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TD	<i>Peltophorum dubium</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	3.7
Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TD	<i>Prunus persica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.0
Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TTD	<i>Malus domestica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.0

Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TTD	<i>Peltophorum dubium</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	3.7
Paudel <i>et al.</i> 2013	TTD	<i>Prunus persica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	4.0
Peters <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Larix decidua</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	16.5
Peters <i>et al.</i> 2017	TD	<i>Picea abies</i>	stem segment	Coniferous	15.9
Prendergast <i>et al.</i> 2007	T-max	<i>Actinidia chinensis</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	9.5
Shackel <i>et al.</i> 1992	SHB	<i>Prunus persica</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	6.3
Smith <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Acacia holosericea</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Smith <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Acacia holosericea</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	NA
Smith <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Smith <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	NA
Smith <i>et al.</i> 1995	CHP	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	NA
Sperling <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	whole plant	Monocot	60.0
Steppe <i>et al.</i> 2010	CHP	<i>Fagus grandifolia</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	18.0
Steppe <i>et al.</i> 2010	HFD	<i>Fagus grandifolia</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	18.1
Steppe <i>et al.</i> 2010	TD	<i>Fagus grandifolia</i>	stem segment	Diffuse-porous	18.0
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Liquidambar styraciflua</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	7.5
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Pinus echinata</i>	without roots	Coniferous	7.5
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Pinus taeda</i>	without roots	Coniferous	7.5
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Populus deltoides</i>	without roots	Diffuse-porous	7.5
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Quercus alba</i>	without roots	Ring-porous	7.5
Sun <i>et al.</i> 2012	TD	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	without roots	Ring-porous	7.5
Swanson & Whitfield 1981	CHP	<i>Nothofagus solandri</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	11.0
Swanson & Whitfield 1981	CHP	<i>Pinus radiata</i>	whole plant	Coniferous	5.0
Urban <i>et al.</i> 2012	SHB	<i>Humulus lupulus</i>	without roots	Ring-porous	NA
Vellame <i>et al.</i> 2010	SHB	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	whole plant	Diffuse-porous	1.4

1143

1144 Table S2. Anova summary of the LMM models, using the same structure as objective 1,
 1145 comparing calibrations reported in SFD and SF units (Units) for CHP and TD. CM
 1146 (Calibration material).

Method	Calibration metric	Variable	Sum sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F.value	Pr(>F)	
CHP	<i>Ln-Ratio</i>	Units	0.086	0.086	1	52.051	1.088	0.302	
		CM	0.196	0.098	2	44.433	1.241	0.299	
	<i>Slope</i>	Units	0.074	0.074	1	25.274	0.368	0.550	
		CM	0.238	0.119	2	40.068	0.591	0.558	
	<i>Slope (ln-ln)</i>	Units	0.001	0.001	1	12.350	0.020	0.890	
		CM	0.137	0.069	2	22.131	0.913	0.416	
	<i>Z-Cor</i>	Units	1.075	1.075	1	20.769	4.304	0.051	
		CM	4.635	2.317	2	34.981	9.279	0.001	
	TD	<i>Ln-Ratio</i>	Units	0.049	0.049	1	26.720	0.407	0.529
			CM	0.141	0.071	2	16.643	0.580	0.571
<i>Slope</i>		Units	0.165	0.165	1	44.722	2.279	0.138	
		CM	0.170	0.085	2	14.837	1.168	0.338	
<i>Slope (ln-ln)</i>		Units	0.223	0.223	1	72.669	2.179	0.144	
		CM	0.145	0.072	2	29.275	0.708	0.501	
<i>Z-Cor</i>		Units	0.077	0.077	1	26.073	0.284	0.598	
		CM	0.017	0.009	2	17.409	0.032	0.969	

1147

1148 Table S3. Summary of the LMM models of *Ln-Ratio* (accuracy), *Slope* (proportional bias), *Slope (ln-ln)* (linearity) and *Z-Cor*
1149 (precision) as a function of Methods and Calibration material (CM; Whole plant: whole plant on a container or lysimeter; No-roots:
1150 whole plant without roots). CHP is the reference level for the variable Method and Stem segment is the reference level for CM,
1151 corresponding to the model intercept. All other coefficient estimates indicate the difference relative to the intercept. σ^2 is the within-
1152 groups random variability (residuals of the model). τ_{00} is the between-group random variability. N is the number of levels within
1153 random groups. ICC is the Intraclass Correlation Coefficients of each random group. R^2_m and R^2_c are the variability explained by the
1154 fixed and the random factors, respectively.

Coefficients	<i>Ln-Ratio</i>			<i>Slope</i>			<i>Slope (ln-ln)</i>			<i>Z-Cor</i>		
	Estimate	Conf. Int.	p-value	Estimate	Conf. Int.	p-value	Estimate	Conf. Int.	p-value	Estimate	Conf. Int.	p-value
Fixed effects												
(Intercept)	0.186	-0.052 – 0.425	0.129	0.957	0.779 – 1.135	<.001	0.847	0.719 – 0.976	<.001	2.317	1.982 – 2.653	2.317
<i>Method</i> (T-max)	-0.186	-0.611 – 0.240	0.395	-0.273	-0.584 – 0.038	0.089	-0.085	-0.312 – 0.142	0.463	-0.082	-0.669 – 0.506	-0.082
<i>Method</i> (HR)	-0.278	-0.510 – -0.047	0.019	-0.043	-0.247 – 0.162	0.683	0.058	-0.106 – 0.221	0.488	0.16	-0.205 – 0.525	0.16
<i>Method</i> (HFD)	-0.206	-0.409 – -0.003	0.048	0.013	-0.167 – 0.193	0.886	0.000	-0.143 – 0.143	1	0.541	0.220 – 0.862	0.541
<i>Method</i> (SHB)	-0.374	-0.843 – 0.095	0.124	-0.04	-0.365 – 0.285	0.809	0.184	-0.058 – 0.427	0.139	0.45	-0.170 – 1.070	0.450
<i>Method</i> (TD)	-0.652	-0.847 – -0.457	<.001	-0.205	-0.368 – -0.041	0.015	0.283	0.160 – 0.406	<.001	-0.125	-0.423 – 0.173	-0.125
<i>Method</i> (TTD)	-0.625	-0.941 – -0.310	<.001	-0.219	-0.503 – 0.066	0.134	0.203	-0.016 – 0.421	0.072	-0.372	-0.877 – 0.133	-0.372
<i>CM</i> (Whole plant)	-0.028	-0.300 – 0.245	0.841	-0.127	-0.317 – 0.064	0.197	-0.139	-0.276 – -0.003	0.05	-0.667	-1.034 – -0.301	-0.667
<i>CM</i> (No-roots)	-0.133	-0.394 – 0.128	0.319	-0.081	-0.298 – 0.135	0.463	-0.055	-0.213 – 0.104	0.503	-0.775	-1.172 – -0.379	-0.775
Random effects												
σ^2		0.091			0.1			0.076			0.278	
τ_{00} , <i>Specie</i>		0.013			0.004			0.013			0.04	
τ_{00} , <i>Study</i>		0.159			0.041			0.004			0.184	
N_{Specie}		65			65			65			65	
N_{Study}		48			48			48			48	
ICC _{<i>Specie</i>}		0.049			0.029			0.137			0.08	
ICC _{<i>Study</i>}		0.604			0.284			0.048			0.366	
Observations		290			290			290			290	
R^2_m		0.200			0.077			0.215			0.280	
R^2_c		0.723			0.366			0.361			0.601	